

Original Paper

The New Challenge of Education Value and Limits of Distance

Learning Today

Annalisa Grammegna^{1*}

¹ Pegaso International, Smart City Malta, Unit 605 SCM01 Ricasoli, Kalkara SCM 1001, Malta, Italy

Received: March 25, 2020

Accepted: April 3, 2020

Online Published: April 9, 2020

doi:10.22158/jecs.v4n2p59

URL: <http://dx.doi.org/10.22158/jecs.v4n2p59>

Abstract

Covid 19 has brought economy, development and culture to its knees, the cornerstones of every nation. Internationally, Italy appears to be among the first countries to be infected, red areas signs regions from north to south, there is a real war. Every single individual appears destabilized, deprived of freedoms, compressed by reasons of collective health. Maintaining serenity in the family context appears difficult in this moment that has also taken away the possibility of honoring death by crying their dead.

In this scenario “we are all aware of the challenge that the country is facing and in order to mitigate the situation of social isolation connected to the drama we are experiencing, the school is on the front line. The culture it is considered a decisive factor for our country to know how to fight overcome and win the battle in course”, says the note of Ministry of Education. The school imposes itself in the life of families in a new context, the home walls with the digital teaching, the fulcrum of this research, to allow teachers to maintain interaction ad instance with the pupil. The present research aims to highlight strengths and limitations of distance teaching, giving voice, through a specific questionnaire, to parents and pupils of sample classes in Naples. The results emerged testify to the undisputed role of the human teacher / learner relationship and the need for support the school audience with computer literacy, providing telematic means and tools.

This is to guarantee today the right to education for all in full respect of art. 3 and 34 of the Italian constitution.

Keywords

education, distance learning, teaching online

1. Introduction

The historical moment we are experiencing is “exceptional”, where this term is used in his deeper meaning. The globalized world fights against an invisible enemy, a virus, insidious and lethal, which devastates the soul of the individual and the community, paving the way for paths of fear and mistrust in against others.

Italy’s red zone, especially Lombardy, is at the end of its forces but fights and resists. In these days we are in spasmodic search of news and information to feed the thread subtle of the hope and to give a semblance of normalcy to hard daily life.

In Campania and in Puglia, we observe the return of people whom, by despising sometimes moral and precautionary provisions descend from Northern Italy to reunite with their family members Understandable desire, but in my opinion not justifiable in this situation given the priority protection of the right to collective health.

Normal people every minute demonstrate that they are extraordinary, risking their lives for the neighbor “only” to satisfy the sense of duty, with stoic self-sacrifice they do their I work without hours, locking fears in a corner of soul, without pauses, without to be able to see family members “sine die”.

At the moment, in fact, estimates are not possible, it is not known when this war will end so like defined by Macron, who in one of the daily television broadcasts claimed “we are at war”. The so-called Angels of Italy, doctors, nurses, technicians, health workers live in a deep abyss pharmacists, and still railway workers, law enforcement, firefighters, transporters and all those who they guarantee the supply and distribution of goods.

In this moment of great psychological and emotional instability, the family first agency educational finds a past dimension and in some ways no longer known, where time appears as a forgotten variable. Relationships and dynamics are rebuilt and reinvented, restoring value to the concept of freedom; freedom now compressed from multiple points of view, at least reduced and certainly desired.

“Staying at home” TV spot, continuous warning to the masses, is an obligation sanctioned to preserve and defend the community. The powerful are called to rediscover the transience of the human being because the virus does not spare nobody, there are no social classes, no space barrier is able to stop its spread, heads of government, politicians and parliamentarians must identify new priorities and every day is a race against time to make decisions, for then paying the price tomorrow.

All systems are put to the test and everyone is called upon to make their own contribution to the best.

The world of adults, teens and children is turned upside down and maximum attention is given to function educational when the nation requires closed schools throughout the country. Here is the school, the second training agency, called upon to reinvent roles, methods and means to better manage this emergency, imposing itself as a necessary presence, in the life of each, committed as per decree to adopt distance teaching.

However, this implementation method presupposes skills and means that are not always available in equal measure on the whole national territory since investments in training very often in the recent

decades have been neglected by successive policies. No later than last November, the Italian minister of Miur himself denounced the absence of funds dedicated to education after a series of executives who had made only wild cuts unconditional. As reported in: “IL FATTO QUOTIDIANO” of November 6, 2019, a national newspaper. The real strength of a people is given by culture and we are right now really “weak”. In Campania, southern region often remembered by the black chronicles, but almost never spread for merits, not least those today in the medical where there is a study led by a team of doctors, to counter COVID 19. In Campania my region the research in question starts, which aims to highlight the value and limits of distance learning in one emergency situation such as today, in real time.

In the first decades of the third millennium in today’s computerized society, children are definable such as digital natives. Very often there has been a disconnect between the educational offer and the request of users characterized by new needs for speed and diversity of teaching methodologies increasingly computerized.

And here is that the coronavirus present on a global level requires smart working. The latter it has multifaceted faces from the use of institutional school platforms, to the forwarding of emails, rather than creating folders, online videos, activities and networking. This poses perplexity for teachers, pupils and for the parents themselves. The former see their own educational function reduced and debased, marginally relegated, enclosed in an explanatory and private video in its entirety of empathic relationship, smiles of tacit understanding, of a facial gestural mimic language unequivocal, of the value of the silence of the diversity of individualized interventions personalized, the only ones capable of giving everyone the right recognition. According to Carl Rogers, the pupil-centered learning, largely depends on the teacher’s behavior that postulates “ability to advise, support, support, encourage to promote mature and autonomous personalities, capable of self-educating themselves in the future.

The effectiveness of the educational action therefore also depends to a large extent on the daily relationship that is established between teacher and pupil. A good relationship will facilitate knowledge, know-how, and to know to be.

The great absentee decreed by covid 19 is precisely the daily educational relationship between teacher and pupil, who in the didactic relationship leads to an emotional and aiming attunement to the educational equality.

Training report that adjusts the school model to the needs of each individual pupil, protagonist in a democratic society to which he himself is educated. Overcoming physical barriers, the virtual lesson poses new questions and modus operandi also to children who, despite being born digital, accustomed at in the presence, to the debate in the classroom, to the relationship with the reference teachers, they see themselves deprived of daily interpersonal relationship. Not only that, at the closing of the school, is associated educational loneliness since there is no peer group, without class, there is not, the help of the companion, the conversation, the discussion and the constructive quarrel. The context of peers natural oasis of reference is denied. This is perhaps the true victory of the teaching, in a forced

way, COVID19 has taken away freedom, spaces of association, has changed the daily operating methods of billions of people in the nation, but has given way to understand how irreplaceable it is technology however, is the human relationship that holds the primacy and qualifies existence itself. Our to be is a being together. The same bewildered and worried parents are forced to reassess the teaching function often debased and deprived of just social recognition. They find themselves immersed in a family landscape in the practical difficulty of following the children, not only in a subsidiary way but as builders of their children's educational path.

They find themselves in the front line invested with a role not really, they clash with the need to put in place compensatory measures and stratagems to make up for the lack of strategies, methodologies and teaching. Everyone has knowledge and skills, but being an educator cannot be reduced to mere transmission of notions, the greatest and daily difficulty of the teacher is given by find the channel individual and proper to each student to transfer knowledge transforming it into skills.

Starting from the real situation of today's uncertainty, the writer structures this research for highlight values and limits of distance learning. In aid it seems useful to recall the note of the Ministry of Education of 18 March 2020 according to which "distance teaching to be such requires reasoned construction targeted teaching materials through an interaction between teachers and pupils. Whatever the means by which teaching is practiced, the aim and principles do not change. In the awareness that nothing can fully replace what happens in classroom presence, it is still a matter of giving life to an "unusual learning environment" for ... create, ... remodel from time to time.

The direct or indirect connection, immediate or deferred, through video conferences, video lessons, group chats, reasoned transmission of didactic materials through the uploading them to digital platforms and the use of class registers in all of them teaching support functions, interaction on interactive systems and apps preparatory digital education: all this is distance learning. Distance teaching necessarily poses direct requests for training, basic computer literacy for access to platforms, hardware tools such as computers and printer or even a valid WI FI network. Another digital criticality emerging from the use of distance learning is related to the evaluation and verification, the need arises to rethink the evaluation framework in different terms to orient it skills through targeted teacher training. The teacher is the true mediator between the family and socio-cultural context of this period which, with poverty of means and criticality, he reinvents himself every day to show the world that the school despite all the difficulties is present and will always be there as an institution.

The statistical surveys carried out are drawn on the basis of the preparation of questionnaires, first structured and then administered electronically to a sample of parents primary school children of the passing classes, such as elementary V classes and class III of secondary school.

The research aims on the basis of the data collected to highlight how these we could define indispensable prerequisites are not in possession, nor always present in every family context, in particularly in the western part of Naples.

Have you ever had other distance learning experiences before this compulsory school closing period?

Do you own a PC?

Do you have a printer?

Do you find it easy to access the most used institutional school platforms?

In his opinion, the pupil feels more the lack of distance learning:

Does the pupil consult the electronic register alone to download schoolwork?

In this particular historical moment, does distance learning help the pupil?

WhatsApp text messages have a different weight today, in your opinion are they able to bring teachers and learners closer together?

Online videos and explanations, can they meet the needs of the pupils?

Would it be more useful to collaborate online through group activities and forums?

Graphically, it highlights how distance teaching certainly helps children and parents, but it is self-limited because it lacks its own and irreplaceable peculiarities typical of face-to-face relationship. From the global findings of the responses submitted, online videos and explanations seem to be positive, for a high percentage, responding to pupils' needs (question n9).

The results of this research, if generalized and extended, would represent a snapshot of the today's situation in Campania, highlighting the need already revealed by MIUR for funds for hardware technologies and training.

It appears mandatory then to highlight, the overload requested at the teacher, summarized in the ten skills required by P. Perrenoud to the modern teacher for the development of knowledge metacognitive that the teacher is looking for in this emergency to manage:

1. Organize and animate learning situations,
2. Manage the progression of this
3. Design and evolve differentiation devices,
4. Involve pupils in their learning and work
5. Working in and with the team,
6. Participate in the management of the school
7. Inform support and involve parents
8. Use new technologies
9. Address the ethical dilemmas of the profession

10. Manage your continuing education

Perhaps after Covid 19, from what emerged and put into play, the voice of teachers will be heard more. To the teachers in the field are asked for a thousand skills and a thousand faces, they are called to building together, with a view to enhancing this function also at a social level, one school certainly different, but functional, responding to the rights of everyone and above all a participatory school.

References

Carl Rogers - Da persona a persona il problema di essere umani ED. Astrolabio Ubaldini.

F.Cuccurelli lavoratori della conoscenza la rivista rubriche. (2014, July 31).

G.De Vecchi aiutare ad apprendere.

La societ`a come ordine educante in AaVV la scuola Brescia. (1965)

La solitudine degli iperconnessi, internet nuove normalit`a e nuove dipendenze -Matteo Lancini.

Manuale delle metodologie e Tecnologie Didattiche Simone edizione.

Metacognizione ed apprendimento il mulino Bologna. (1995).

Perrenoud, P. (2014). Dieci competenze per insegnare Anicia Roma.

Tapia M.n Educazione e solidariet`a la pedagogia dell'apprendimento Rome. (2006).

Tommaso Zanella Raffaello Cortina editore.

V. Andreoli L'educazione (im)possibile Rizzoli Milan. (2015).